

The Echoes of Inner Conflicts: The Importance of the Study of the Representation of Trauma in Indian Literature in English

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***Abstract:** This article explores the depiction of trauma in contemporary Indian narratives in English focusing on five primary texts by regional writers. Through these narratives the study addresses diverse forms of trauma, including gendered trauma, the trauma of sexual identity, and traumas linked to societal oppression, displacement and marginalisation. The narratives here are explored through the lens of trauma theories both western and regional, confirming the need to study trauma in the cultural and socio political context of the Indian society. The article also shows how trauma is individual and collective in Indian narratives, and how the representative techniques of trauma the like fragmented memory, symbolism, identity and resistance play an important role in the understanding of trauma and the processes of its healing. Drawing from various interdisciplinary studies, this article highlights the significance of examining the representation of trauma in Indian narratives to uncover the root causes of trauma in Indian society and explore potential paths for healing.*

Keywords: Trauma, Indian literature, Interdisciplinary, Memory, Marginalisation, Gender, Sexual Identity.

Introduction of Trauma

Trauma often engenders a profound and pervasive silence, which can be considered one of its most insidious effects. It defies quantification, being inherently subjective and resistant to verbal expression. Its impact transcends immediate understanding, penetrating deeply into the psyche where it remains largely unresolved. Like a persistent spectator, it recurrently surfaces in consciousness, inflicting damage that seems irreparable.

The study of trauma in literature is now, a trending field that offers profound insights into the human condition and the ways in which individuals and societies navigate experiences of profound suffering. In fact, it's the need of the hour with mental well-being, being the most discussed topic of contemporary times. In the context of Indian literature, the representation of trauma is particularly significant, given the rich tapestry of cultures, languages, and histories that characterize the subcontinent. This research aims at exploring the importance of studying trauma in Indian literature, with a focus on selected contemporary works from various vernacular languages that have been translated into English. It argues that such study is crucial for gaining a deeper and more accurate understanding of the changing voices in Indian society and culture, and for recognizing the unique ways in which trauma is experienced and represented in this context.

Trauma is the Greek word for "wound" According to American Psychological Association (APA) trauma is "an emotional response to a terrible event like an accident, rape, or natural disaster." This psychological reaction to emotional trauma now has an established name: *post-traumatic stress disorder*, or PTSD. The literary definition of trauma refers to the representation and exploration of psychological and emotional wounds, distress, and lasting effects resulting from deeply distressing or disturbing experiences in literature, including novels, poetry, and other forms of storytelling. Cathy Caruth is a prominent figure in trauma studies and her theory of trauma in literature has had a significant

impact on the field. Her work, particularly in the books "Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History" (1996) and "Trauma: Explorations in Memory" (1995), has shaped how we understand trauma in literary texts. In her book *Unclaimed Experience* she defines trauma as "In its most general definition, trauma describes an overwhelming experience of sudden or catastrophic events in which the response to the event occurs in the often delayed, and uncontrolled repetitive appearance of hallucinations and other uncontrolled phenomenon". (11) Sigmund Freud's definition of childhood trauma, from his work "Beyond the Pleasure Principle" (1920), is: "The event, the trauma, which is pathogenic [disease-causing] and the process which leads from it to the illness, are not identical with each other. The trauma is the moment at which the normal, the course of life, is interrupted; illness is the subsequent, often lifelong, accommodation" (Freud, 1920, p. 14). His observations on the representation and effects of trauma go a long way in helping in the process of understanding the behavioural patterns of individuals be it in real or in narratives.

Judith Herman developed a comprehensive understanding of complex trauma and coined the term "Complex PTSD." She highlighted the psychological and emotional impacts of prolonged or repeated trauma, particularly in cases of interpersonal abuse or captivity. Her work emphasizes the importance of safety and empowerment in the healing process. "When trust is lost, traumatized people feel that they belong more to the dead than to the living." (Herman p. 52).

Janina Fisher contributed to the field of trauma by exploring the impact of trauma on the body and integrating somatic approaches into therapy. According to her the mind has a way of storing up memories and feelings, keeping them tucked away from our daily awareness. This can sometimes result in behaviours where a person feels disconnected or detached from reality. She developed the concept of the "trauma capsule," where unprocessed traumatic memories are encapsulated in the body, leading to physical and psychological symptoms.

Contemporary theorist Michelle Balaev's critique of the universal approach to trauma is important for contextualizing trauma within Indian socio-cultural realities. Balaev's insistence on the importance of place, culture, and individual experience in trauma narratives allow for a more nuanced reading of how trauma is represented differently in each of these texts, particularly in relation to caste, gender, and displacement.

Additionally, the field of trauma theory is constantly evolving, and new perspectives continue to emerge over time. Overall, trauma studies in literature have evolved to encompass a wide range of topics and perspectives, reflecting the ongoing importance of understanding how literature can illuminate the human experience of trauma. It provides a space for critical analysis and empathetic engagement with the complex narratives of suffering and survival in the literary world.

Trauma and Literature

Sigmund Freud's work on psychoanalysis in the late 19th and early 20th centuries laid the foundation for understanding how traumatic experiences could affect the human psyche. His ideas expressed in his books *Introduction to Psychology* (1917) and *The Interpretation of Dreams* (1920) about repression, trauma, and the unconscious mind greatly influenced subsequent discussions of trauma in literature. The aftermath of World War II saw a surge in literary works that explored the traumatic experiences of soldiers and civilians. Writers like Kurt Vonnegut (e.g., "Slaughterhouse-Five") and Joseph Heller (e.g., "Catch-22") used dark humour and satire to depict the absurdity and horrors of war. The Holocaust had a profound impact on literature, and survivor testimonies like Elie Wiesel's "Night" and Primo Levi's "If This Is a Man" became important works in the study of trauma. These texts grapple with the unimaginable horrors of the Holocaust and the long-lasting psychological scars it left on survivors. Feminist scholars have played a significant role in trauma studies, examining how gender and sexual trauma are represented in literature. Works like Toni

Morrison's "Beloved" explore the trauma of slavery and its effects on African American women. The advent of critical theories such as postcolonialism and postmodernism expanded the scope of trauma studies. Scholars began to investigate how colonialism, displacement, and cultural trauma are portrayed in literature. Philosopher Martha Nussbaum, suggests that literature is a major part of developing one's relationship to the world and to others. In her 1997 book *Cultivating Humanity: A Classic Defence of Liberal Education*, she argues that,

“citizens can't think well on the basis of factual knowledge alone” and instead, must cultivate what she calls “the narrative imagination” (44). She defines this as, “the ability to think what it might be like to be in the shoes of someone different from oneself; and to understand the emotions and wishes and desires that someone so placed might have, including the many ways in which social circumstances shape emotions and wishes and desires” (44). Later, in her book *Not for Profit: Why Democracy Needs the Humanities* (2010), she reiterates her ideas about literature almost word-for-word:

“Citizens cannot relate well to the complex world around them by factual knowledge and logic alone. The third ability of the citizen, closely related to the first two, is what we can call the narrative imagination. This means the ability to think what it might be like to be in the shoes of a person different from oneself, to be an intelligent reader of that person's story, and to understand the emotions and wishes and desires that someone so placed might have.” (95)

Contemporary literature continues to engage with trauma in diverse ways, addressing issues such as war, terrorism, immigration, and identity. Collective trauma and personal trauma are distinct yet interconnected concepts that involve experiences of overwhelming distress and disruption. While personal trauma refers to individual experiences of suffering, collective trauma involves the psychological and emotional impact of traumatic

events on groups, communities, or societies. These events can include natural disasters, wars, genocides, or societal injustices. Collective trauma can affect the shared beliefs, values, and identity of a community or society. The Holocaust is a collective trauma that profoundly affected not only the survivors but also future generations of Jewish people, leading to a lasting impact on their cultural identity and collective memory. In recent times the 9/11 terrorist attack is also an example of collective trauma.

Significance and Impact of Trauma in Indian Narratives in English

In India, events such as colonialism, partition, caste and class, poverty, and diasporic trauma have been the basis of collective trauma which have left deep scars on the psyche of the nation. This is clearly reflected in its art and culture, and writers have continuously explored this theme in their narratives. From Indian English literature to Indian Writings in English these themes have been explored extensively. While collective trauma is a generalized and objective phenomenon, it takes on a subjective dimension when viewed through the lens of individual experience. The impact of a traumatic event on an individual's personality can vary significantly, with differences in the degree of suffering and its lasting effects. It is widely understood that pain resulting from trauma is not easily comparable due to its deeply personal nature.

Personal or emotional trauma refers to individual experiences of severe distress or harm that overwhelm a person's ability to cope. It often results from events such as physical or sexual abuse, natural disasters, accidents, or witnessing violence. Personal trauma can have long-lasting effects on an individual's mental, emotional, and physical well-being. For example, a person who has experienced childhood abuse may struggle with trust and intimacy in relationships throughout their life. A survivor of a car accident may develop post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and experience flashbacks and nightmares. Trauma, whether brief or chronic, can profoundly impact individuals, shaping their lives in various ways.

Chronic trauma, stemming from severe experiences such as the loss of a loved one, violent encounters, rape, abuse, or torture during childhood or early years, can persist in the psyche, exerting enduring effects. Often, these traumatic events become deeply ingrained in the victim's memory, influencing their personality, decision-making processes, and ability to adapt socially, sometimes without their conscious awareness.

The study of trauma in the Indian context is crucial due to its unique social and cultural background. India's diverse religious, linguistic and regional identities contribute to a complex tapestry of narratives and experiences. Vernacular Indian languages reflect the diverse cultural social and historical contexts of the country offering a more nuanced portrayal of trauma than works by Indian authors in English. By the translation of these works in English, scholars and readers are exposed to a wider range of perspectives and experiences, enriching their understanding of Indian society and complexities. One of the key reasons for studying translated Indian literature is its ability to provide a more authentic depiction of Indian life as well as evoke empathy, awareness and social changes.

In postcolonial Indian literature the portrayal of trauma is diverse and nuanced, capturing the intricacies of Indian society and its complex histories marked by violence, oppression and struggles with identity. It serves as a lens to explore how people and communities navigate the lasting effects of colonialism, caste, gender and sexual discrimination. Indian literary works provide a rich landscape for delving into the ways trauma is felt and depicted. Authors writing in both English and regional languages have examined the aftermath of historical and social violence often mirroring the psychological and emotional effects of trauma on their characters and communities.

The five chosen works of fiction in this research showcase various manifestations of trauma providing a holistic perspective on how different dimensions of trauma are represented within Indian

storytelling. The authors use various narrative techniques like symbolism, fragmented memory, flashback, non-linear narration, snapshot etc. to portray the themes of traumas of gender, identity and displacement and marginalization. It provides valuable perspectives on how both individuals and communities navigate through challenging experiences. Michelle Balaev in her book *Contemporary Approaches in Literary Trauma Theory* (2014) has asserted that for a more comprehensive framework for understanding trauma in literature it is necessary to go beyond the traditional psychoanalytical models and include a broader range of contexts. The theme of trauma must be analysed from all dimensions: literary, psychological, cultural, social, political and historical.

Geetanjali Shree's *The Roof Beneath Their Feet* (2019) delves into the emotional and psychological struggles faced by women in a male dominated world. The story uses the roof as a symbol to represent both a space where characters navigate their identities and confront their inner turmoil. Through fragmented memories and visions the book captures the hidden traumas of women residing at the edges of society. Characters like Chacho and Lalnagrapple with psychological and emotional scars of domestic abuse and societal expectations, their suffering is depicted as an unspoken and overlooked pain. "The roof was both refuge and prison. It allowed them to escape, but at the same time, it held them captive to the past." The roof serves as a powerful metaphor for both liberation and confinement. It provides a refuge from the scrutinizing eyes of the world yet it also embodies a fragile threshold where past wounds linger. "But the roof was also a reminder. A reminder of what was left unsaid, undone. It held memories that weighed down on Lalna like a second skin, refusing to let go." Although the roof provided an escape from the scrutinizing eyes of the world yet it reminded Lalna of past wounds which haunted her. It symbolizes how trauma confines individuals within their own memories and emotions.

Chacho is a victim of domestic abuse, Lalna struggles with her own identity and the narrator is unable to cope with the trauma of being a silent witness to both Chacho and Lalna's vulnerabilities, and maintaining the secrecy of their relationship due to societal pressures. By examining the characters experience, it is possible to gain insights into socio- cultural context of India which is plagued by gender based inequality.

The second novel by the same author, *The Tomb of Sand* (2021), which won the International Booker Prize, delves into the theme of intergenerational trauma of Partition but from a deeply personal and gendered perspective. The story follows a woman who rediscovers her true self later in life and journeys across borders bravely confronting the haunting memories of her past. By intertwining historical events with personal recollections, the novel weaves, a layered narrative of grief, displacement and resilience. Throughout the novel the author resorts to the art of non-linear storytelling blurring the lines between past and the present. Anupurba's journey is marked by the profound impact of childhood trauma as she strives to break free from the cycle of pain and hardship that has haunted her family for years. Through a series of flashbacks and recollections Anupurba begins to piece together the broken memories of her childhood and unearth the buried secrets of her family.

In this novel Shree uses the symbol of walls and doors to represent barriers to freedom and also the keeper of secrets. "The walls of the house stood silent, unmoved by the screams and sobs that once filled the rooms. They had witnessed everything and yet said nothing, sealing the secrets within."

"A tomb stands still, encasing stories of those buried beneath it, but the sand blows over, shifting endlessly. Trauma is both: the fixed weight of the past and the restless erosion of memory." This line beautifully captures the contrast between the static nature of a tomb, symbolizing the weight of historical trauma, and the shifting,

fragmented nature of sand, symbolizing the impermanence and instability of memory.

Dharmapadajena and Kalyana Samantray have in their article “Traumatic Experiences and their Representation in Narratives: A Study” discussed the challenges in representing trauma in literature due to its unspeakable nature, fragmented consciousness and difficulty in direct linguistic representation. Henceforth, the authors have to resort to the various narrative techniques in representing trauma in literature. Its depiction is important to portray the complex and distressing nature of traumatic experiences, to create empathic and impactful narratives, resonate with trauma victims and aid in the healing process through a deeper understanding of it.

Arupa Patangia Kalita's novel *The Loneliness of Hira Barua* published in 2016 delves into the impact of violence and displacement in Assam especially on the women folk. The trauma of gender, marginalisation and victimisation is strikingly brought out to light. The main character Hira Barua goes through both and emotional upheaval as she tries to come to terms with losing her home, identity and sense of belonging. The book also explores the political turmoil in north-eastern India by employing silence, repetition and displacement as literary techniques to depict the characters psychological turmoil.

In the stories of *The Loneliness of Hira Barua* water and rivers serve as symbols for the flow of life and the gradual wear away of one's identity and surroundings. They reflect the pain of being uprooted from familiar surroundings and the ‘invasion of inner spaces’ as mentioned by Manashi Bora in her article *History Memory and Trauma in Selected Works of Arupa Patangia Kalita*. Through the lens of trauma these narratives tackle societal issues like gender inequality, caste discrimination and sexual marginalization showcasing the complex interplay between personal trauma and shared histories marked by violence and displacement.

Vasudhendra's Mohanaswamy (2016) examines the struggles of homosexuality, internalized homophobia and caste bias within a rural Indian setting. Through the character of Mohanaswamy, the author Vasudhendra unravels the traumatic experiences of people born with queer choices in an orthodox and unaccepting society. They live a life filled with dual trauma, as they find it extremely difficult to come to terms and accept their own identity as well as face the backlash of a society that is not inclusive of them. This novel focuses on the personal struggles, emotional impact, social stigma, secrecy and shame and how these factors affect and shape the personality of the protagonist. His loneliness and rejection are portrayed as deeply traumatic experiences. Interestingly the author Vasudhendra is himself a gay activist and in one of his interviews by Preethi Nagraj of Hindustan Times on July 1st 2017 admitted that coming out of the closet was an easier task for him than many others-as he is "upper" caste, affluent and a global citizen in many ways. But this is not so with many Indians with queer sexual choices residing in rural India, like the protagonist in his novel, Mohanaswamy.

The non-linear progression of chapters, delve into various aspects of the main characters journey. This fragmented narrative style reflects the turmoil Mohanaswamy goes through as he confronts societal ostracism stemming from his sexual orientation and caste background. There is a shift from rural to urban spaces and so on, symbolising the socio-cultural differences in these spaces.

Sachin Kundalkar's *Cobalt Blue* (2013) addresses the trauma of sexual identity and societal rejection in a conservative Indian family. The novel's split narrative between a brother and sister, both in love with the same man, reflects the psychological trauma of navigating non-normative sexualities in a society that refuses to accept them.

Cobalt Blue explores the impact of societal rejection on the emotional well-being of a brother and sister as they reflect on their relationships with the same man. The dual narrative highlights how

trauma can distort one's sense of self and relationships with others. The novel uses the colour blue to symbolize melancholy, longing and love mirroring the protagonist's tumultuous journey through unfulfilled desires and societal disapproval. Through fragmented memories the characters live with the pain of love that defies societal norms serving as a bittersweet reminder of both joy and sorrow. Cobalt Blue portrays the challenges faced by the siblings Tanay and Anuja, due to their sexual preferences in a conservative, heteronormative society showcasing the emotional toll of concealing one's true self facing familial ostracism and navigating unrequited love as forms of deep-rooted trauma.

Cultural, historical and personal factors play a role in shaping how we process traumatic experiences. This perspective challenges the idea that trauma is universally experienced according to Western theories and highlights how specific contexts influence how we express our traumas. By looking at trauma through this lens we can better understand India's distinct social realities, the lasting impact of colonialism the complexities of trauma and the significance of collective memory. Renowned scholar Anup Dhar focuses on the history of psychoanalyses in India through the works of Girindrasekhar Bose, who was a stalwart in the field of proto-psychiatry in India and was also the first Indian to earn a doctorate in psychology.

While examining trauma narratives, it is firstly important to understand the history, nature, aspects, and factors of trauma, and for this we refer to the origin of trauma study and the works of trauma theorists. His discussion over trauma theories with Sigmund Freud through the exchange of letters, which lasted for almost two decades, clearly states his disagreement over some of the former's theories, like the concept of consciousness, the Oedipus complex, the role of culture, and the origin of neurosis. Since this study relates to the study of representation of trauma in Indian narratives, it becomes very essential to examine the root of psychoanalysis in India and how it differs from Western concepts.

These themes shed light on the variety of ideas and influences that have affected the discussion of psychoanalyses in India.

J. Roger Kurtz in his book *Trauma and Literature* (2018) examines trauma in relation to cultural context and how it is experienced and represented differently across cultures. It also states that reading and writing about trauma can have therapeutic effects, helping both readers and writers deal with and heal from traumatic experiences. Perspectives from psychology, sociology, and cultural studies have been incorporated, showing that an interdisciplinary approach is essential for a full understanding of trauma in literature. Literature about trauma can raise awareness about social issues, influence public discourse, and contribute to societal change by highlighting the long-term effects of traumatic events on communities. By exploring these themes, *Trauma and Literature* offers valuable insights into how literature can both reflect and shape our understanding of trauma. Irene Visser's chapter in this book 'Trauma in Non-Western Context' highlights the significant contribution of postcolonial and non-western scholars in the redefining of trauma theories away from the traditional Freudian psychoanalyses.

Literary works often capture these traumas in ways that are fragmented, symbolic and deeply moving making this exploration both intellectually enriching and socially impactful.

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